

IT- and machine learning-based methods of classification: The cooperative project ClaReNet – Classification and Representation for Networks

Chrisowalandis Deligio², Caroline von Nicolai¹, Markus Möller¹, Katja Rösler¹, Julia Tietz¹ Robin Krause², Kerstin P. Hofmann¹, Karsten Tolle², David Wigg-Wolf¹.

¹ Römisch-Germanische Kommission des Deutschen Archäologischen Instituts.
² Big Data Lab, Goethe University Frankfurt.

Abstract

The classification of archaeological finds and their representation are shaped by various object epistemological approaches and changes of medium. With ever increasing digitisation, there are now new possibilities of classification, for example using methods of automatic image recognition, as well as the representation of finds on the web with linked open data.

ClaReNet, a cooperative project of the [Römisch-Germanische Kommission](#) (German Archaeological Institute) and the [Big Data Lab](#) (Goethe University Frankfurt), funded by the **Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF; Federal Ministry of Education and Research)**, tests the possibilities and limits of new digital methods of classification and representation. To this end, traditional approaches of typification and the recording of attributes in numismatics and archaeology are compared with IT-based methods of classification, including deep learning, using the examples of three Celtic coin series that were each chosen to address particular research questions and problems.

This paper briefly introduces the approach of object epistemologies before considering Celtic coins as scientific objects and the history of research on them with regard to classifications and typologies. Using the example of a series of coins from *Armorica* (Brittany), we will present how deep learning and algorithms can classify the coinage, how this may or may not differ from traditional classifications by numismatists, and the lessons that are to be learned from this exercise. The paper concludes with an evaluation of the IT-based methods used in the project, as well as an outlook on further possibilities for research into the classification and representation of Celtic coins.

keywords: Celtic coinage, machine learning, object epistemologies, knowledge practices, science and technology study, die studies, classification.

Introduction

Humans gain knowledge about the world through objects, both in everyday life and in science. Our ways of knowing and our approaches change in the process, not only because of different

conceptions of the world and related questions, but also because of research practices and technologies, as well as the empirical examples and observations chosen, all of which interact. This in turn will always affect the classification and representation of objects of knowledge, in our case Celtic coins. For example, there are cultural evolutionist approaches that establish typological series on the basis of imitation and degeneration of the images on the coins, whereas cultural history approaches have described the spatio-temporal occurrence of certain coin types in typographies and tried to assign them to historically transmitted Celtic tribal designations. Our approach here, in contrast, is based on production-technological observations – such as die studies – that create fine chronological sequences of coins.

The project ClaReNet, short for “Classifications and Representations for Networks. From types and characteristics to linked open data for Celtic coinages”, which officially started on 1 February 2021, is a cooperative project of the Römisch-Germanische Kommission of the Deutsches Archäologisches Institut (RGK) and the Big Data Lab of the Goethe University Frankfurt. It is funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research in the framework of research on theoretical, methodological and technical developments in the digital humanities¹.

For the project, three examples of Celtic coin series with very different characteristics were chosen, each one to address particular research questions and problems (fig. 1)²:

The ‘bushel’ *quinarii* from southern Germany and northern Switzerland are characterised by the successively more abstract image of the head on their obverses and the combinations of various symbols around the horse on the reverse³. Several classifications have already been established for them using traditional methods of numismatics. In the course of the project, the different classifications will be re-assessed with methods of artificial intelligence (AI) and systematically compared with respect to performance on the data. The aim is to observe whether there are similarities between the classifications and, if so, to see how the classifications can be harmonised.

¹ For further information on the project see the ClaReNet blog <https://clarenet.hypotheses.org>; on the funding initiative <https://www.geistes-und-sozialwissenschaften-bmbf.de/de/Digital-Humanities-1710.html>.

² For more detailed information on the three coin series and their relevance for the project see the relevant pages of the project blog: <https://clarenet.hypotheses.org/numismatics>.

³ Numismatic terms are explained in the *Glossar* of the project blog: https://clarenet.hypotheses.org/glossar_num.

Coin series 1 - Bushel *quinarii*

Coin series 2 - *monnaies à la croix*

Coin series 3 - *Coriosolitae*

Fig. 1: Examples of the coin series examined in the project. The differences in shape and form also become clear within the individual coin series (photos: Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen zu Berlin, Bernhard Weisser [Public Domain Mark 1.0]; graphics: M. Möller).

For the second series, the *monnaies à la croix*, the representations of the head on the obverse and the symbols in the fields of the cross on the reverse of the coins are to be analysed by computer-assisted classification methods. The focus lies on understanding the combination of features in the designs of the coins. The starting point is Eneko Hiriart's recent classification (Hiriart 2017). In addition to the images, the descriptions of the coins provided by E. Hiriart will also be integrated into the analysis by applying methods from Natural Language Processing⁴.

The third series, the billon stater coinage which is attributed by numismatists to the *civitas* of the *Coriosolitae* in modern Brittany (*Armorica*), offers a very different challenge arising from the availability of a massive stock of digital images of some 70,000 coins from the recently discovered coin hoard of Le Câtillon II (Jersey, UK). The aim is to assist the numismatists working on classifying the coins and to observe how far AI methods can work with the dataset independently. The dataset⁵ is sorted by using unsupervised methods⁶. A central question in carrying out the work is to see to what extent the computer and human classifications of the

⁴ Natural Language Processing is a subfield of AI, focusing on analysing and interacting with human language (Natural Language Processing with PyTorch, D. Rao and B. MacMahan, 2019, Chapter 2).

⁵ On our definition of dataset see <https://clarenet.hypotheses.org/it-teil4>.

⁶ For further information on supervised and unsupervised methods see <https://clarenet.hypotheses.org/it-teil1>.

coinage correspond, or whether the AI suggests a different classification to that developed by numismatists using traditional, non-digital methods.

Using these examples, ClaReNet aims to test the possibilities and limits of new digital methods of classification and representation. The project consists of three strands:

1. Traditional approaches of typification and the recording of attributes in numismatics and archaeology will be compared with IT-based methods of classification, including deep learning and automatic image recognition⁷.
2. Representation is addressed by setting up an online portal or virtual union catalogue, Online Celtic Coinage (occ.dainst.org), for the coin series under investigation, following the paradigm of portals such as Online Coins of the Roman Empire (OCRE)⁸ that are based on the vocabulary and ontology of nomisma.org⁹. The catalogue will be linked to publicly accessible online collections and research databases. This will require the development of an ontology to cover the specificities of Celtic coinage.
3. The third strand consists of a science and technology study (STS) to document the production and circulation of knowledge, as well as to instigate reflection on changes in cognitive processes resulting from the use of digital tools and algorithms. A particular focus of the study is on **Path dependencies, Actor Networks and Digital Agency (PANDA)**¹⁰.

In this paper, we focus on the chances and limitations of machine learning methods for the automated classification of large numbers of coins, using the example of the coin series 3, the coinage of the *Coriosolitae*. For this purpose, we first look at how Celtic coins have been studied and classified in the past, before turning to the question of automated classification. Celtic coins as scientific objects in the past

The traditional approach: classifications and representations in Celtic numismatics

Coins are generally flat metal objects stamped with an impression on both sides. They are mobile, multi-medial objects that combine form, material, image and (in the case of Celtic coins only sometimes) text. In regard to typologies and classifications, it is important to understand how the coins we study were manufactured: the blanks and dies were made by hand, and they were also struck by hand. In this way, they differ considerably from today's standardised, machine-made Euro coins, which are all identical in shape and form. Celtic hand-made coins, on the contrary, even those belonging to the same type and struck with the same dies, can differ significantly from one another (fig. 2).

⁷ For definitions of the IT-terminology used here see “What’s the Difference Between Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Deep Learning?”: <https://blogs.nvidia.com/blog/2016/07/29/whats-difference-artificial-intelligence-machine-learning-deep-learning-ai/>.

⁸ <https://numismatics.org/ocre/>.

⁹ <https://nomisma.org/>.

¹⁰ <https://clarenet.hypotheses.org/sts-teil3>.

Fig. 2. Left: modern, standardised Euro coins vs. Celtic, hand-struck bushel quinarii. Right: manufacture of Celtic coins with a hand-held die (graphics left: M. Möller, photos: Archäologische Staatssammlung München; drawing right: Sabine Schade-Lindig, hessenARCHÄOLOGIE).

This form of manufacture presents particular challenges for classifications and typologies¹¹, and it should be noted that in numismatics there is no universal or consistent concept of what exactly constitutes a type or a class. Both terms are used irregularly and are often confused. Furthermore, it was only in the second half of the 19th century that Celtic coins became the subject of serious scientific interest. Previously, they were regarded as vile and degraded derivatives of Greek and Roman originals (Forrer 1908, 1). In a mixture of cultural evolutionist and cultural historical approaches, they were classified according to material, design and the geographical distribution of finds. Relative chronology was established on stylistic criteria, absolute chronology on the basis of datable Mediterranean prototypes they were presumed – often incorrectly – to copy (Forrer 1908, 16-21). Moreover, until well into the 20th century, the opinion prevailed that hardly any two Celtic coins were identical, i.e. the number of variants was almost as great as the number of individuals (e.g. Blanchet 1905, 71). Consequently, a “disparité indéfinie des espèces gauloises” (an unlimited variety of Gaulish coins) (Colbert de Beaulieu 1973, 14) was assumed. It was considered almost impossible to identify two coins with identical impressions.

From past to present

The earliest attempt at producing a comprehensive reference work illustrating types of Celtic coins was Henri de La Tour's ‘Atlas de monnaies gauloises’ produced in 1892 (de La Tour 1892). The Atlas was based on the catalogue of Celtic coins in the collection of the

¹¹ https://clarenet.hypotheses.org/clareterms_typologie.

Bibliothèque nationale de France in Paris published three years earlier by Ernest Muret and Anatole Chabouillet (Muret / Chabouillet 1889). The coins were attributed to tribes known from written sources (fig. 3), mainly on the basis of the geographical distribution of the coin finds. But such attributions do not necessarily reflect the actual authorities behind the production of coins in the pre-Roman Iron Age. We now know that not only tribes but also confederations, *pagi*, and powerful individuals minted coins (Ziegeus 2010, 17-18; on the *pagi* see Roymans 1990, 23-26). Today a tendency can be observed to replace tribal affiliations with references that are considered to be more neutral, such as names for types based on a find spot (e.g. ‘Martbeger Typ’) or the iconography (e.g. ‘potins au sanglier’), or else, above all by British numismatists, on geographical areas (e.g. Haselgrove 1987 and 1999, Leins 2012). But even here there is a certain reluctance to completely abandon tribal attributions.

Fig. 3: Billon coins attributed to the *Curiosolitae* or *Coriosolitae*, represented in the “Atlas” of de La Tour (de La Tour 1892, pl. XXII).

Representation of coins in Celtic numismatics

If de La Tour's Atlas was originally conceived as an illustrated and selected representation of the collection of the Bibliothèque nationale de France in Paris, it has since served as a reference work with the drawings of individual coins being used as representatives of individual coin types or classes. This practice of using a single image as a representative (called “ideal type”, “modèle type” or “dessin idéalisé” in numismatics) still persists today, for example in the most recent typology for the coinage of Iron Age Britain, *Ancient British Coinage* (Cottam et al. 2010) (fig. 4) or E. Hiriart's corpus of the *monnaies à la croix* (Hiriart 2017, 20); this in spite of the fact that it does not do justice to the individuality of Celtic coins and the wide variation between examples of the same type. It suggests that “types” were fixed and standardised, a concept that was adopted from the much older disciplines of Greek and Roman numismatics and is reflected in reference works such as *Roman Imperial Coinage* (Mattingly 1923). For many coinages produced in the Celtic world, what we in fact find is a development of the imagery on the coins over time, one that does not always proceed in a straight line as a typological series in the sense of Oscar Montelius. Sometimes it is gradual, sometimes in more obvious steps (cf. Hofmann 2014).

Rulers unknown
GOLD STATERS

ABC 482

Westerham South gold stater. SO4-5. Wreath motif, crescents and cloak./ Disjunct horse l., stick legs and many pellets above. VA 202, BMC 24-32, Ev.B6, ALA, M 29, S 21. *Scarce*.

ABC 485

Selsey Two-Faced gold stater. SO5-6. Wreath design with two hidden faces./ Triple-tailed horse r., wheel below, charioteer's arms above. VA 210, 212-5, BMC 445, 447, 449-54, Ev.B9, Al.QA, M 58, S 38. *Scarce*.

Fig. 4: Representation of British gold staters in the reference work “Ancient British Coins” (Cottam et al. 2010, 47), here with regional affiliation (Code SO for Southern region). Note the desire to still name at the top a minting authority if possible.

It's all about context

A change in mindset that departs from the purely antiquarian approach to Celtic coins has come about since the 1980s, much influenced by Iron Age archaeology. Above all, archaeological contexts are now included in the interpretation of coin finds, which has led to significant revisions in the chronology of Celtic coinage. As Colin Haselgrove states, “Detailed analysis of association, stratigraphy and site context are fundamental if coinage is to be systematically related to other components of material culture and society. Moreover, both archaeological and cultural context are fundamental to the interpretation of every coin find.” (Haselgrove 1987, 11-12; see also Polenz 1982, 48-49). Much work is now focussed on producing ever finer chronologies for Celtic coins, not just for the sequence of types, but also the sequence of production within types.

Die studies: ‘charactéroscope’

So-called die studies can be used to determine the chronological order in which dies were used and coins were produced. This method essentially consists of identifying the specific characteristics of each individual coin die, and assigning to them the individual coins produced with it in order to create groups. The assumption is that if coins are indeed struck with the same die they should share a common origin in time and/or place. Furthermore, since the dies used for the obverse (in English the “heads” side) and reverse (“tails”) will normally not both have been replaced at the same time, but when one or the other became too worn or broken, it is possible to establish the sequence in which dies were used and a group of coins produced (Goebel 1972) (fig. 5c).

Die studies were developed as early as the 19th century in Greek numismatics (de Callataÿ 2007), but were only used in Celtic numismatics for the first time in 1948 by Jean-Baptiste Colbert de Beaulieu (Colbert de Beaulieu 1948), before finally being firmly established in the field by him in the 1970s. Previously Celtic coins had been considered an “impenetrable chaos” unsuited for such studies (Colbert de Beaulieu 1973, 17; on the history of the use of die studies in Celtic numismatics see de Jersey 2016). J.-B. Colbert de Beaulieu's work was strongly influenced by French structuralism, the predominant intellectual movement in France at the time, the aim of which was to uncover the fundamental elements and regularities within the respective fields of research. Consequently, J.-B. Colbert de Beaulieu also referred to his set of methods as “numismatique structurale”, the most important of which was the analysis of die links, that is coins produced with the same dies, which he called “charactéroscope” (from Ancient Greek *χαρακτήρ*, coinage, and *σκοπία*, observation; Colbert de Beaulieu 1973, 40-41).

In the application of die studies to Celtic coins, it is important to note that while the mints of imperial Rome were tightly structured institutions that could produce dies of the same coin type that look very similar, it is assumed that the process of die production and minting in the Celtic world was less centralised, often resulting in dies with the same motif that look very different and are thus more easily distinguished, making them particularly suitable for die studies.

Praxis: How does a die study work?

Fig. 5c illustrates how a die study can be used to determine the sequence of production. It shows a coin (coin 1) which was produced with dies that we shall call obverse 1 and reverse 1. From a technical point of view, the reverse is struck by the upper, mobile die, the obverse by the lower, fixed die (see fig. 2; 5a). In our example, there is a second coin (coin 2) produced with obverse 1 but with a different reverse die, reverse 2. A third coin was produced with reverse 2, but with a new obverse die 2. Sometimes we find groups of coins struck with the same dies, and in our example coins 4 and 5 were both produced with obverse 2, but with a new reverse 3. Coin 6 is produced with the same reverse 3, but now with a new obverse 3, and so on... Such sequences can tell us a great deal about the way in which the production of coinage was organised. This is also discussed below.

Fig. 5: a. Immobile lower die for a *quinarius* of the Treveri from the Donnersberg, Germany; b. Class VI staters of the *Coriosolitae*; c. Visualisation of a die study of staters of the *Coriosolitae* (photos, a: Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum Mainz; b,c: Jersey Heritage; graphics: D. Wigg-Wolf).

More than a lifetime's work

Die studies carried out by eye are extremely time consuming and tedious. This is why we are looking at how machine learning and automatic image recognition can help with this task, and what new ways of sorting coins are emerging as a result. As more or less standardised, mass-produced artefacts for which there is a huge amount of photographic material, coins provide an ideal testbed for such methods. Anwar et al. (2019) already used Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to distinguish the central features of a set of Roman Republican silver denarii, but such projects generally worked with high quality images of well-preserved coins, not on the kind or amount of poorly preserved and inconsistently photographed material that we were confronted with. Other numismatic projects have already benefited from the use of CNNs to classify coins based on a typology or by mint, with promising results¹². Feature matching approaches such as Taylor (2019) or Heinecke et al. (2020) have produced excellent results for die studies, but again the material used consisted of well-preserved precious metal coins.

For the coinage of the *Coriosolitae*, one of the three coin series studied in the project, we have access to images of nearly 70,000 coins from the hoard of Le Câtillon II (de Jersey 2016; de Jersey 2018; de Jersey 2020). Some coins from the hoard were found by two metal detectorists in 2012 in a field on the island of Jersey, some 15 metres from the location of another coin

¹² <https://www.corpus-nummorum.eu> and <https://zenodo.org/records/10424274>.

hoard, Le Câtillon I, which was discovered in 1957 (Gruel 1990). The discovery of the first coins resulted in further excavations that led to the discovery of the main body of the second Le Câtillon hoard. It is the largest Celtic coin hoard ever found, and was lifted as a block weighing approximately 750 kg, before being painstakingly excavated in the Jersey Heritage laboratory (fig. 6).

Fig. 6: The hoard of Le Câtillon II on the island of Jersey contained nearly 70,000 coins. Due to the size, its analysis poses a great challenge for numismatics (photo: P. de Jersey, States of Guernsey, Culture and Heritage).

The coinage of the *Coriosolitae*

Apart from the coins, the find also contained eleven gold torques, silver and gold jewellery, silver and copper ingots, glass beads, a spearhead of a type dated to the Bronze Age, as well as a worked stone. Some 70% of the coins in the hoard are staters that are attributed to the *Coriosolitae*, but the find also contains smaller coins (quarter staters and pieces known as *petits billons*) as well as a number of staters of other polities from north-western France and Britain. The staters of the *Coriosolitae* are made of billon, an alloy of copper and silver in which the amount of silver is less than 50 %. A typical motif on the obverse of the coins is a stylised head surrounded by strings of beads. On the reverse, there is often a human-headed horse with a charioteer, surrounded by symbols such as a boar, a winged figure, a multi-spoked wheel and a lyre, as well as other symbols that are not always easy to identify from our modern perspectives. The staters generally weigh between 6 and 7 g. The coin hoard has been dated to

the 40s or perhaps the 30s of the 1st century BC, meaning that the find dates to the period after the Roman conquest of Gaul (de Jersey 2016; de Jersey 2018).

Colbert de Beaulieu presented the first typology of the staters of the *Coriosolitae* in 1957. He divided them into six classes (I-VI) on the basis of the shape of the nose and the eyes of the head on the obverse (Colbert de Beaulieu 1957). In the late 1970s and early 1980s, Katherine Gruel, then a doctoral student of Colbert de Beaulieu, further developed his typology and added other variants (Via, Vib, Va, Vb, Iva, Ivb) to this classification, based mainly on the symbols on the reverse (Gruel 1981). Her typology, as well as the relative chronology of the coin series based on it, were the result of one of the first such studies to employ computer-based statistical analysis such as seriation of the data from coin finds, and are still considered to be valid today. The discovery of the hoard of Le Câtillon II now offers the possibility of testing the validity of the typology, based on a very large number of coins. For this purpose, we are analysing the coin hoard in cooperation with the domain expert Philip de Jersey, who is currently working on it.

Classification with Artificial Intelligence: machine learning

Obtaining the necessary information on nearly 70,000 coins and classifying them requires a great deal of working time. In particular, de Jersey estimates that the ongoing die study would take several more decades. One of our goals was therefore to find methods to assist him and to evaluate the extent to which AI, and more precisely *machine learning* (ML), can help in the process of classification. ML encompasses AI methods that learn generalised concepts based on data. These tasks usually fall into the category of weak AI, i.e. the solution of a specific problem. Furthermore, the performance of the machine learning methods that were applied on the dataset will be observed and used to question the underlying classification. This means asking the question if the ML approach has problems in identifying a given human defined classification and if yes, why?

There are two approaches to machine learning that we have tried so far:

1. Unsupervised approach: this approach works with data that is not yet labelled, e.g. only the coin photos are used. If labels have already been assigned, the analysis can also be done independently of them.
2. Supervised approach: in this approach the data is labelled with additional information from a domain expert, who defines, for example, to which group, or in our case to which die a coin belongs (this labelled data is known as the ground truth).

In the following, the basics of these methods are explained before presenting the preliminary results of our studies.

Convolutional Neural Networks

In the field of image classification, so-called CNNs are today state-of-the-art¹³. As noted above, other numismatic projects have already benefited from their use to classify coins based on a typology or by mint, with promising results, although other methods such as feature matching have been preferred for die studies.

CNNs are machine learning algorithms intended for image data and usually used in supervised learning tasks. A CNN consists of several layers, typically convolutional layers followed by a pooling layer and dense layers (explained below). A CNN can be assembled as desired, but there is also the possibility of using structures that are already successful¹⁴. In our case, we use a well-known structure, VGG16 (Simonyan / Zisserman, 2015). The network consists of 16 layers, 13 of which are convolutional and the remaining three dense. Pooling layers are not counted individually and follow after a number of convolutional layers (for a deeper introduction and visual representation of VGG16 see: <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/vgg-16-cnn-model/>).

The convolution layer (based on the VGG16 approach) is the name-giving layer of the algorithm. In such layers a sliding window (size 3x3 pixels) is moved over the input image; this sliding window is also called kernel or filter and contains different weights. These weights are trained and adjusted by the CNN in the training phase. As it moves over the image, it performs a mathematical operation called a dot product, which multiplies the selected area by the weights (fig. 7 an example with a 2x2 pixels sliding window). During training based on ground truth data, the result of the overall network is compared with the given annotation within the ground truth. In a back propagation phase the relevant weights are amplified if the training was successful in selecting the correct outcome, or weakened if not.

Fig. 7: While the convolutional layer (on the left with a 2x2 pixel kernel) uses a subset of the input with the sliding window, each input of the dense layer (on the right) considers all outputs of the previous layer. (C. Deligio).

Typically, **pooling layers** are set after convolutional layers. A pooling layer eliminates pixels in an image while preserving the semantics of the image content (Moroney 2020, 35-36). There

¹³ <https://paperswithcode.com/sota/image-classification-on-imagenet?p=centroid-transformers-learning-to-abstract>.

¹⁴ <https://pytorch.org/vision/stable/models.html>.

are different types of pooling such as 1) average pooling, where the average in the area being considered is calculated, 2) min(imum) pooling, where the smallest value, or 3) max(imum) pooling, where the highest value is chosen. The VGG16 CNN uses 2x2 max pooling layers. By doing this, the amount of information is reduced while the features are kept (fig. 8).

A **dense layer** is a fully meshed layer. This means that the outputs of the previous layer are all connected to each input of the dense layer, resulting in high computational cost. These costs are much higher compared to a convolutional layer, since in a convolutional layer only the inputs (outputs of the previous layer) of the sliding window are connected and calculated for the output. (Di et al. 2018). For each of these connections, weights are again used and trained during the training phase. Therefore, dense layers are usually set at the end of a CNN, due to the extensive computational resources needed. For example, when used as the last layer the size corresponds to the number of classes. This is then also called the classification layer.

Fig. 8: Example of the input (left) and output (right) of a 2x2 max pooling layer (C. Deligio).

Taking all weights into account, the VGG16 architecture consists of about 138 mio. Parameters and the trained model needs a corresponding amount of space (the VGG16-model of ImageNet has a size of 528 MB¹⁵).

Clustering: k-Means

The cluster algorithm we use in combination with CNN is k-Means (Patel 2019), which belongs to the group of unsupervised algorithms. Instead of learning based on human-provided data (ground truth), as in supervised learning, the goal is to independently recognize common patterns or rules in the dataset. For k-Means the input data of objects are transformed into a vector representing a point in an n-dimensional space. This allows the algorithm to define distances between the points and to group them in so-called clusters. This means that objects of one cluster are more similar (based on the distance function and the way the data are transformed into their vector) to each other compared to those in other clusters. For k-Means

¹⁵ <https://keras.io/api/applications/>.

the number of expected clusters (k) must be specified, although finding an optimal value for k presents significant difficulties if there is insufficient information on the distribution in the dataset. There are methods such as the elbow method that use a heuristic approach to calculate an optimal value for k . This it does by iterating over a set range for k . In our case in combination with the CNN backbone this calculation is computationally expensive and therefore not an optimal fit. In case the information of the classes would not be known, a run can be performed with a selected k and depending on the manual evaluation of the result, k can be increased or decreased.

While this seems ideal for setting up a classification, unfortunately the results can also be very unexpected, especially for images where each pixel will be handled independently and no structures such as edges or larger structures are identified that can contextualise the pixel, as would be the case with CNNs. Therefore, a combination of CNN and cluster algorithm is recommended. In this way, the CNN extracts the features while the cluster algorithm groups them together.

Clustering the coinage of the *Coriosolitae*

For the coins of the *Coriosolitae*, we decided to initially use unsupervised machine learning methods, for which we need only images without additional information, in order to create a pre-sorted dataset. We opted for an algorithm known as DeepCluster, where deep neural networks are combined with clustering algorithms, as developed by Mathilde Caron and her colleagues (Caron et al. 2018). The method combines a CNN and a clustering algorithm, such as k-Means, to build classes. The most important criteria for choosing this algorithm was that it does not require any further information from a domain expert and the approach outperformed competing algorithms based on existing challenges like ImageNet (Caron et al. 2018, table 3).

In the DeepCluster approach¹⁶, the images are distributed by the cluster algorithm and the resulting clusters are passed on to the CNN as pseudo-classes. By repeating the iteration process multiple times, the classification should improve. The CNN searches for similar features in the clusters, and the extracted features are then used as input for the cluster algorithm, which in turn forms a new distribution (fig. 9).

Fig. 9: Illustration of the DeepCluster method approach (after Caron et al. 2018, fig. 1).

¹⁶ <https://github.com/facebookresearch/deepcluster>.

Image data preprocessing

Before feeding the CNN with image data, preprocessing steps are needed to prepare the data. In our case, each image includes the coin, a scale and the assigned ID. In order to avoid the algorithm being biased by the scale or other elements of the image not representing the coin, we first cut out the coin (fig. 10). To do so, we used object detection to automatically detect the coins on the images¹⁷. The detected object is marked by a so-called bounding box, and the image is then cropped to the area of the bounding box.

Fig. 10: Object detection methods are used to automatically crop the coins on the photos provided by our project partners (photos: Jersey Heritage; graphics: C. Deligio).

Before the cropped images are made available to the CNN, scaling follows. It is possible to choose any size, but the larger the images are, the more processing power is typically required. Also, if a pre-trained network is used, it is recommended choosing the size that it has been trained to. For our process, the images are scaled to 224x224 pixels (height \times width), which corresponds to the trained size of the VGG-16 network. When scaling, care should be taken not to lose the proportions and levels of detail.

DeepCluster experiment – unsupervised

In order to use the algorithm, the number of clusters, k , has to be defined. Caron et al. 2018 recommend choosing a significantly larger k than there are classes, and since we have an idea of the expected number of classes for the *Coriosolitae* coins, namely six according to the numismatic classification (see above), a value of $k=50$ was chosen for the results presented here.

For our first experiments, due to the limited processing power initially available, we used only some 25,000 coins, each with an obverse and reverse image. We treated each side of the coins as individual images without indicating any correlation between the two. The aim was to use the selected algorithm in order to group the coins according to similarity. We also intended to explore the possibilities of employing a supervised method, as this step is important from the point of view of verifying or challenging the traditional numismatic classification of the coins.

¹⁷ https://github.com/tensorflow/models/tree/master/research/object_detection.

If the clusters formed are similar to the classification, this would to a certain extent confirm the validity of the classification.

Of the 25,000 coins, the domain expert de Jersey determined that 1072 belong to one class of coins, namely class VI. Using this information, we could track the coins identified by him in the clusters created and evaluate how the algorithm grouped or distributed them.

In our experiment, one of the 50 clusters consisted of 1162 images containing 860 of those 1072 coins identified by the domain expert to belong to class VI. This means that at least 74% of the verified coins in this class were successfully grouped together by the algorithm. Unfortunately, the algorithm does not provide any details on how and why the clusters were formed. Fig. 11 shows parts of good and less optimal cluster. The evaluation of the clusters was done manually, but within the framework of our project, it was not possible for us to carry out the time-consuming work of evaluating all clusters precisely.

Fig. 11: left, a cluster with a high similarity; right, a mixed cluster (photos: Jersey Heritage; graphics: C. Deligio).

After this first experiment, the expert provided us with an additional table with information about the entire dataset that had been created by him and his team of volunteers who worked on photographing, identifying and classifying the coins. The new table allowed us to evaluate the result more accurately, as it was now possible to check all clusters. We identified 17 clusters with obverse images and 12 clusters with reverse images that contained 70 % or more coins that were assigned to one of the six classes. It should also be noted that the method was able to cluster coins that were in a poor state of preservation, i.e. fragmented, corroded, etc. It also successfully separated obverses and reverses into different groups! However, it should be noted that some other clusters generated by the algorithm were less convincing.

Overall, we are very pleasantly surprised by the results. We are thus optimistic that we can help the domain expert in classifying the 70,000 coins in the hoard. In addition, the similarity of the distribution by machine and domain experts also provides some confirmation of the validity of the existing classification of coins by numismatists. In our case, the machine result goes hand in hand with the expert classification, even having the same problems. Most of the mixed clusters consist of coins of classes IV, V and VI: numismatists have similar problems deciding

to which of these classes some coins should be assigned. Also the domain experts confirm that the evolution of the coins is more a continuous transformation and that clear borders between some classes do not exist.

Furthermore, the clusters containing coins with a poor state of preservation could also be helpful. Some of these coins cannot be classified at all, or only by experts well acquainted with the material. Thus, the identification by the machine of such problematic coins could help to avoid the time-wasting step of giving such coins to team members who do not have the appropriate knowledge. The same is true for supervised approaches we went on to set up. The clusters that have a high correspondence with the expert's identifications were relevant for our further work. Since they have been confirmed by human and machine, they could provide a good starting point for an approach based on supervised methods.

Die study experiment – supervised

In another approach we used a supervised method that also combines a CNN with the k-means algorithm, but in a different way. The aim in this case was to recognize not classes but the products of the individual dies used to strike the coins. We concentrated on the coins of Class VI since the domain expert P. de Jersey had already carried out a traditional die study of the class based on physical observation and measurement. In this approach a CNN was trained using the results of the die study as a ground truth. The features (vectors) forming the results of the last convolutional layer were extracted by the trained model and then used as input for the k-means algorithm.

In a first test conducted by Robin Krause as part of a bachelor thesis (Krause 2020), 1200 coins class VI were used as input. When he carried out this initial work, only 50 % of the coins had then been assigned to individual dies by the domain expert. Subsequently the attributions of all of the coins to individual dies were provided by the domain expert, facilitating an evaluation of the initial test. Since we now knew that 36 different dies from the data set were used, the number of desired clusters was also set to 36 ($k=36$).

Figure 12 shows the result of this approach. On the left the results for two clusters are evaluated against the ground truth at the time R. Krause did the initial work and only 50 % of the coins had been attributed to a die. On the right the same clusters are evaluated after P. de Jersey's die study was completed. In the upper two diagrams it is clear that in cluster 1 the algorithm successfully grouped together 38 coins produced with the same obverse die. On the other hand, dies for which only a few examples existed in the dataset were poorly grouped, as in cluster 23. It is therefore indeed possible to distinguish the individual dies with the help of AI, but a reasonable number of previously verified images is required for the method to be successful. Just how many depends, however, on the given problem. We intend to apply this approach to the full set of images of the staters of the *Coriosolitae*.

Incomplete die study (2020 – ca. 50% labelled)

Completed die study (2021 – 100% labelled)

Fig. 12: Examples of the supervised clustering approach combining a convolutional neural network with the k-means algorithm. Upper row: a cluster containing coins struck by only one die. Lower row: a cluster containing coins from multiple dies (graphics: R. Krause).

Conclusions

In this machine learning section we have presented two different tasks and raised the questions:

- Can unsupervised methods support the presorting of a huge coin set and if yes, to what extent?
- Can supervised methods help to recognise dies.

For the first question, we started by treating the dataset as a case study of a new find, with no information available at the start. Unsupervised learning was used to see how far the dataset could be sorted or grouped, and whether it could even match the expert’s classification. While we had already seen promising results in the manual evaluation, once we compared the clusters with the classification by the domain expert, the potential was confirmed. The expert classification was well reflected in the clustering results and some strong clusters were formed,

while other clusters are less convincing. In total we can say: unsupervised methods can help to presort, but the results cannot be used without correction and approval by an expert.

For the second question: We were able to obtain quite good results for dies for which there were a large numbers of examples. But it should be noted that poorly represented dies (few or only one example) were not well grouped. Another main problem here is the need for training data (ground truth). In later approaches we therefore switched to image matching (ORB) and doing a pairwise comparison between the coins. Results could even be improved and no training is required.

Outlook

The next step of the ClaReNet project will be to look at two other coin series, the bushel *quinarii* from southern Germany and Switzerland and the *monnaies à la croix* from southern France (fig. 1). The main challenge posed by the bushel *quinarii* results from the fact that the depiction of the head on the obverse grows more and more abstract over time, gradually becoming a tuft or bushel. Due to this gradual nature of process, it is not as easy to divide the bushel *quinarii* into classes as it is for the coinage of the *Coriosolitae*. This development poses great challenges not only for numismatics, but also for machine learning techniques. We thus hope to combine different approaches in order to harmonise the existing classifications, of which there are several, and make fluid transitions in the development of the designs on the coinage apparent, while at the same time taking manufacturing processes into account. Another challenge will be classifying coins that are difficult to assign, for example because the symbols on the reverse that characterise individual classes are often not visible on the coins. The question will be whether it is possible to classify such coins with AI-based methods and whether the numismatic community will then accept the decision.

For the *monnaies à la croix* we are faced with the challenge that there are a large number of types that are defined by the combination of the symbols in the fields of the cross on the reverse, but generally relatively few, or sometimes even no, images available to us for each one. To address this challenge, we intend to extract information from the type descriptions and to use the information gained in this way as a starting point for image recognition methods. One option we have in mind is to use the extracted information in order to connect similar type descriptions, thus effectively providing more images per type group.

Furthermore, the introduction of machine learning methods not only has great potential for work on classifications. It also provides a particularly suitable moment for fundamental discussions about research practices, changes in object epistemologies and of media, and the interplay of theories and methods in the context of concrete empirical case studies. This requires – especially in interdisciplinary projects – conceptual work. Therefore, we are currently trying to present in a transparent manner the different terminologies and concepts used by experts, for example classification and typology, in a wiki called ClaReTerms, which is publicly accessible on the project blog (<https://clarenet.hypotheses.org/clareterms>). It is only through the combination of the history of science, STS and current method evaluation of the

different subjects involved that it is possible to reflect on research paths in all their complexity and on their impact.

The digital revolution in particular promises new insights into the classification of mass products such as coins. Our initial findings suggest that these no longer even need to be highly standardised. However, close cooperation and intensive exchange between AI, various scholars and domain experts will always be a basic prerequisite in order to obtain results that are of value for the experts, in our case archaeologists, numismatists and computer scientists. AI cannot and will not replace human experts, but is a new important player in the field, and one that will change the game.

Literature

Anwar, Hafeez, Saeed Anwar, Sebastian Zambanini, and Fatih Porikli. 2019. ‘CoinNet: Deep Ancient Roman Republican Coin Classification via Feature Fusion and Attention’. arXiv:1908.09428 [Cs], August. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1908.09428>.

Blanchet, Adrien. 1905. *Traité des Monnaies Gauloises*. Paris: E. Leroux.

Caron, Mathilde, Piotr Bojanowski, Armand Joulin, and Matthijs Douze. 2019. ‘Deep clustering for unsupervised learning of visual features’. *ArXiv:1807.05520 [Cs]*, March. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1807.05520>.

Colbert de Beaulieu, Jean-Baptiste. 1948. ‘La trouvaille de monnaies celtiques de Saint-Jacques-de-La-Lande’. *Revue Belge de Numismatique* 94: 15–76.

———. 1957. ‘Le Trésor de Jersey-11 et la numismatique celtique des deux Bretagnes’. *Revue Belge de Numismatique* 103: 47–88.

———. 1973. *Traité de Numismatique Celtique 1. Méthodologie des ensembles*. Vol. 135. Ann. Litt. Univ. Besançon. Besançon.

Cottam, Elizabeth, Philip de Jersey, Chris Rudd, and John Sills. 2010. *Ancient British Coins: ABC for Short*. Aylsham, Norfolk: Chris Rudd.

de Callataÿ, François. 2007. ‘L’historique de l’étude des liaisons de coins (XVIIIe-Xxe s.)’. *Bulletin de la Société Française de Numismatique* 62 (4): 86–92.

de La Tour, Henri. 1892. *Atlas de Monnaies Gauloises préparé par la Commission de Topographie des Gaules et publié sous les auspices du Ministère de l’Instruction Publique*. Paris: Plon & Nourrit.

Di, Wei, Anurag Bhardwaj, and Jianing Wei. 2018. *Deep Learning Essentials*. Packt.

Forrer, Robert. 1908. *Keltische Numismatik der Rhein- Und Donaulande*. Strasbourg.

Gruel, Katherine. 1990. ‘Le Trésor du Câtillon (Jersey 11). Réexamen à la lumière des fouilles et études plus récentes’. In *La Bretagne et l’Europe préhistorique: Mémoire en hommage à Pierre-Roland Giot*, edited by Jean L’Helgouach and Pierre-Roland Giot, 293–98. *Revue Archéologique de l’Ouest. Supplement 2*. Rennes: Langouet.

- Haselgrove, Colin. 1987. *Iron Age Coinage in South-East England: The Archaeological Context*. BAR British Series 174. Oxford: B.A.R.
- Haselgrove, Colin. 1999. 'The development of Iron Age coinage in Belgic Gaul'. *Numismatic Chronicle* 159: 111–68.
- Heinecke, Andreas, Emanuel Mayer, Abhinav Natarajan, and Yoonju Jung. 2021. 'Unsupervised Statistical Learning for Die Analysis in Ancient Numismatics'. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2112.00290>.
- Hiriart, Eneko. 2017. *Catalogue des monnaies celtiques 2. Les monnaies à la croix*. Paris: Bibliothèque nationale de France, Musée d'Archéologie nationale. <http://editions.bnf.fr/catalogue-des-monnaies-celtiques-2-les-monnaies-%C3%A0-la-croix>.
- Hofmann, Kerstin P. 2014. 'Auf der Suche nach der Jastorf-Fibel: Die ältereisenzeitlichen Plattenfibeln Norddeutschlands: Eine Leitform?' In *Das Jastorf-Konzept und die vorrömische Eisenzeit im Nördlichen Mitteleuropa: Beiträge der Internationalen Tagung zum einhundertjährigen Jubiläum der Veröffentlichung 'Die ältesten Urnenfriedhöfe bei Uelzen und Lüneburg' durch Gustav Schwantes 18.-22.05.2011 in Bad Bevensen*, edited by Brandt and Björn Rauchfuß, 129–42. Veröffentlichungen des Helms-Museums, Hamburger Museum für Archäologie und die Geschichte Harburgs. Hamburg: Archäologisches Museum. <https://publications.dainst.org/journals/efb/article/view/2236/6674>.
- Jersey, Philippe de. 2016. 'Colbert de Beaulieu, the Coriosalitae and the Jersey Hoards'. *Revue Belge de Numismatique et de Sigillographie* 162: 159–78.
- Krause, Robin. 2020. 'Clusterbildung keltischer Münzen basierend auf Convolutional Neural Networks'. Johann Wolfgang Goethe-Universität Frankfurt am Main.
- Lévi-Strauss, Claude. 1966. *The Savage Mind. The Nature of Human Society Series*. Chicago.
- Mahoney, James. 2000. 'Path dependence in Historical Sociology'. *Theory and Society* 29 (4): 507–48. Doi: 10.1023/A:1007113830879.
- Mattingly, Harold, and Edward Allen Sydenham. 1923. *The Roman Imperial Coinage. Vol. I: Augustus to Vitellius*. London: Spink & Son.
- Moroney, Laurence. 2020. *AI and Machine Learning for Coders: A Programmer's Guide to Artificial Intelligence*. 1st ed. O'Reilly Media.
- Muret, Ernest, and Anatole Chabouillet. 1889. *Catalogue des Monnaies Gauloises de la Bibliothèque nationale*. Paris: Plon Nourrit.
- Polenz, H. 1982. 'Münzen in Latènezeitlichen Gräbern Mitteleuropas aus der Zeit zwischen 300 und 50 vor Christi Geburt'. *Bayerische Vorgeschichtsblätter* 47: 27–222.
- Rao, Delip, and Brian McMahan. 2019. *Natural Language Processing with PyTorch: Build Intelligent Language Applications Using Deep Learning*. First edition. Beijing ; Boston ; Farnham: O'Reilly. http://digitale-objekte.hbz-nrw.de/storage2/2019/03/03/file_11/8270927.pdf.

Roymans, Nico. 1990. *Tribal Societies in Northern Gaul. An Anthropological Perspective*. Cingula 12. Amsterdam: Najade Press.

Simonyan, Karen, and Andrew Zisserman. 2015. 'Very Deep Convolutional Networks for Large-Scale Image Recognition'. arXiv. Doi:[10.48550/arXiv.1409.1556](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1409.1556).

Taylor, Zachary McCord, 2020. 'The Computer-Aided Die Study (CADS): A Tool for Conducting Numismatic Die Studies with Computer Vision and Hierarchical Clustering'. Computer Science Honors Theses. 54.
https://digitalcommons.trinity.edu/compsci_honors/54.

Ziehaus, B. 1994. *Das Geld der Kelten und ihrer Nachbarn. Sammlung Josef Schörghuber. Ausstellung Vom 28. Oktober 1994 bis 8. Januar 1995 in der Prähistorischen Staatssammlung München*. Ausstellungskataloge Der Prähistorischen Staatssammlung 26. München: Prähistorische Staatssammlung München.

Acknowledgements

We thank the Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung for funding the ClaReNet project and the following institutions as cooperation partners:

Bibliothèque nationale de France, Département des Monnaies, médailles et antiques

Archäologische Staatssammlung, München

Inventar der Fundmünzen der Schweiz, Bern

Université Bordeaux Montaigne, IRAMAT CRP2A

States of Guernsey, Culture and Heritage